

Molecular Identification and Antibiotic Profile of Respiratory Tract *Escherichia coli* and Enterobacter Species Isolated from HIV Patients Attending Gombe State Specialist Hospital, Nigeria

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Abstract

A significant worldwide health burden, respiratory tract infections (RTIs) are particularly destructive to immunocompromised people, such as those living with HIV. Treatment of infections in HIV patients is severely hampered by the advent of multidrug-resistant (MDR) bacteria, such as Enterobacter species and *Escherichia coli*. This study used molecular techniques to identify respiratory tract *Escherichia coli* and Enterobacter species. It assessed the antibiotic profile of the prevalent bacteria among HIV patients attending Gombe State Specialist Hospital from August 2023 to May 2024. Three hundred and ten (310) sputum samples were taken from the ART clinic at Gombe State Specialist Hospital, and cultured for 18–24 hours at 37°C on Blood agar and MacConkey agar. The putative discrete colonies obtained after incubation were identified based on cultural characteristics, Gram staining technique, conventional biochemical tests, and molecular analysis. The results revealed that 121 (39.0%) yielded positive growth of 82(67.77%) and 39(32.2%) for Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria, respectively. The results of phenotypic identification revealed that, all the 39 Gram-negative bacteria were found to be Enterobacter species (25) and *E. coli* (14). Based on the nucleotide BLAST search of the sequenced 16SrRNA genes at the National Centre for Biotechnology, the 16S rRNA identification from two representative bacteria, one isolate each for Enterobacter species and *E. coli* corroborates with cultural, morphological, and biochemical testing, demonstrating that the isolated bacteria belonged to Enterobacter species and *Escherichia coli*. The antimicrobial susceptibility testing showed that the isolates demonstrated varying degrees of susceptibility and resistance to fourteen (14) antibiotics of different classes used in the study. Amoxiclav was more active against *Enterobacter* (20/25, 80.0%) and *E. coli* (14/14, 100%) while Cefotaxime was completely resisted by the *Enterobacter* (11/11, 100%) and *E. coli* (12/12, 100%). High resistance rates were observed for third and fourth generation cephalosporins (Ceftriaxone, Cefotaxime, Cefepime), indicating the possible production of extended-spectrum beta-lactamase (ESBL) by the bacteria. Meropenem, Amoxiclav, and Gentamicin were the most effective antibiotics, showing sensitivity rates above 50% in both bacterial groups. The prevalence of multidrug-resistant (MDR) strains of both

Enterobacter species and *Escherichia coli* was 66.7%, which highlights the need for exploring combination therapy, particularly Meropenem + Amoxiclav or Aminoglycosides + Beta-lactamase inhibitors, to enhance treatment efficacy. Carbapenems (Meropenem), Beta-lactamase inhibitors (Amoxiclav), and Aminoglycosides (Gentamicin) should be prioritized for empirical treatment, given their higher sensitivity rates (>50%) against *Enterobacter* species and *Escherichia coli*. The findings emphasize the urgent need for enhanced antimicrobial stewardship, infection control measures, and molecular surveillance to mitigate the rising threat of MDR *Enterobacter* species and *E. coli* in HIV patients.

Keywords: Respiratory tract Infections, Multidrug-resistant, *E. coli*, Enterobacter species, Antibiotic Susceptibility Profile

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Introduction

Respiratory tract infections (RTIs) are a serious health risk, especially for people with impaired immune systems, such as those infected by HIV (Cribbs et al., 2020). RTIs are a common, diverse collection of disorders that impact both the upper and lower respiratory tract. Lower respiratory tract infections, or LRTIs, are one of the leading causes of morbidity and mortality in the world (Troeger et al., 2019). The interplay between HIV and respiratory infections exacerbates the burden, as PLHIV are more susceptible to opportunistic respiratory disease. The Global Burden of Diseases, Injuries, and Risk Factors (GBD) study, conducted in 2017, found that LRTIs were the sixth most common cause of death across all age groups, accounting for around 2.56 million deaths (Roth et al., 2018). Besides, bacterial aetiologies accounted for more than 50% of LRTI mortality in 2016 (Troeger et al., 2018).

Nigeria, Africa's most populous nation, continues to face significant public health challenges,

particularly in HIV/AIDS and respiratory infections (Muhammad et al., 2017). These conditions not only contribute to high morbidity and mortality rates but also place a substantial burden on the country's healthcare system. As of 2023, Nigeria has the second-largest HIV epidemic in the world, with approximately 1.8 million people living with HIV (PLWH) (Oparaji and Odega, 2023). According to the joint United Nations on HIV/AIDS (UNAIDS), the HIV prevalence rate among adults 15-49 years is 1.3%, with significant regional variations (Nwosu, 2024). In 2022, there were estimated 74,000 new HIV infections and 51,000 AIDs related death in Nigeria (Ogunyinka et al., 2024).

Antibiotic resistance is becoming more widely recognized as a serious global health issue (WHO, 2019), and antibiotic medications are often administered as a component of treatment (Ho 2019). HIV patients infected with MDR bacteria had a far greater death rate than those infected with non-MDR bacterial infections

(Sultana et al., 2021). The substantial rise has severely hampered anti-infection efforts in the incidence of MDR pathogens, especially *Enterobacter* species, carbapenem-resistant *Klebsiella pneumoniae* (CRKP), and *Escherichia coli*, in recent years (Tseng et al., 2018). Monitoring data from the World Health Organization indicates that antibiotic-resistant bacteria are the primary cause of many lower respiratory tract infections and that the number of individuals suffering from these infections is continuously increasing (WHO, 2023). HIV suppresses the immune system, which puts those who are positive for the virus at risk for respiratory issues. The compromised immune system makes them susceptible to opportunistic infections, including those caused by drug-resistant pathogens (Zumla et al., 2014).

Enterobacter is a genus of any group of rod-shaped bacteria of the family Enterobacteriaceae that comprises Gram-negative bacteria classified as facultative anaerobes. The rise of drug-resistant *Enterobacter* species poses a severe hazard to public health. Utilizing horizontal gene transfer, these strains have obtained resistance genes that enable them to resist the effects of several antibiotics (Davin-Regli et al., 2019). Gram-negative and rod-shaped, *Escherichia coli* is also a member of the Enterobacteriaceae family of bacteria (Saleh et al., 2024a; Saleh et al., 2024b). Certain strains of *E. coli* have developed virulence characteristics that allow them to cause illnesses, despite their positive role in the microbiome (Pakbin et al.,

2021). Enteropathogenic *E. coli* (EPEC), Enterotoxigenic *E. coli* (ETEC), Uropathogenic *E. coli* (UPEC) and enterohemorrhagic *E. coli* (EHEC) are among the numerous types of pathogenic strains that have been detected. These strains are linked to distinct clinical manifestations, such as respiratory tract infections, urinary tract infections, hemolytic uremic syndrome, and gastrointestinal infections (Zumla et al., 2014).

HIV and respiratory infections continue to pose significant public health challenges in Nigeria, with millions of lives affected annually (Onovo et al., 2023). While recent statistics provide a snapshot of the burden, critical research gaps limit the effectiveness of prevention and treatment efforts. Research gaps such as Up-to-date epidemiological data, disaggregated data on prevalence and incidence of MDR respiratory infections among HIV particularly in rural areas, co-infection dynamics, Health system research, social determinants, vaccine coverage, and emerging respiratory pathogens hinder effective interventions. Addressing these gaps requires a multidisciplinary approach, involving epidemiologists, clinicians, policymakers, community stakeholders, and others. By prioritizing research and strengthening healthcare systems, Nigeria can make significant strides toward reducing the burden of these diseases and improving health outcomes for its population. This research aimed to determine the occurrence of *E. coli* and *Enterobacter* species from respiratory tract samples of HIV

patients and their antibiotics susceptibility profile in Gombe State Specialist Hospital.

Materials and Methods

Ethical Approval

Ethical clearance was duly obtained from the Research and Ethics Committee of the Gombe State Ministry of Health by the code of ethics for medical research involving human subjects (GS/HSMB/RES/S/Vol.004).

Sample collection

A total of 310 sputum samples were taken from the ART clinic of Gombe State Specialist Hospital for Nine (9) months from August 2023 to May 2024. Samples were collected using a sterile, wide-mouthed, screw-capped universal container (30 ml volume). After that, the samples were taken to the Federal Teaching Hospital Gombe research laboratory for processing. The study's sample size was determined using a standard Fischers formula as described by Charan and Biswas (2013) using prevalence of 25.48% from related study by Maharjan et al. (2022).

Inclusion criteria

HIV confirmed status aged 18 years and above with documentation via medical record and prior testing enrolled at ART clinic of Gombe State Specialist Hospital presenting with symptoms of respiratory tract infections were included in the study.

Exclusion criteria

HIV Patients who received antibiotics treatment within 14 days before sample collection, patients with suspected or confirmed diagnoses of non-respiratory infections, suspected or confirmed tuberculosis, and patients concurrently enrolled in other clinical trials were all excluded from this research

Isolation and Identification of Bacterial Organisms

According to Cheesbrough (2006), the sputum specimens were cultivated on MacConkey agar plates that were prepared per the manufacturer's instructions and incubated at 37°C for 18 to 48 hours. According to Cheesbrough (2006), the putative isolates on the culture plates were identified using biochemical assays, Gram staining, and cultural features.

Gram staining and Microscopy

The colonies of each isolate from an overnight culture were used to prepare a smear by emulsifying it in sterile distilled water on a microscopic slide, air drying it, and then fixed over Bunsen burner flame. After applying a crystal violet stain to the fixed smear for 60 seconds, it was quickly washed with clean water. After applying Lugol's iodine to the smear for 60 seconds, it was washed with clean water once more. Acetone was used to quickly decolorize it, and clean water was then used to wash it. The smear was then washed with clean water and exposed to safranin for one minute. After wiping

the slide's back, it was set in a draining rack to allow the smear to air dry. Finally, a light microscope with an oil immersion objective (x100) was used to examine it under a microscope (Cheesbrough, 2006).

Biochemical reactions

All biochemical tests media were made in accordance with the manufacturer's instructions.

Citrate test

Test tubes were used to create simmon citrate agar. The test organism was streaked down the slope and stabbed into the medium's butt using a sterile straight wire loop. The media was then incubated at 37°C for a whole day.

Indole test

After being inoculated into a test tube with 3 milliliters of sterile tryptone water, the test organism was cultured for 24 hours at 37 degrees Celsius. Following the incubation period, the test tube was gently shaken and filled with 0.5 ml of Kovac's reagent. Within ten minutes, a crimson ring began to form at the interface between the reagent and the infected media.

Urease test

The test organism was inoculated in a test tube containing sterile urease agar by streaking the slope and stabbing the butt then incubated at 37°C for 24 hours. The medium was observed for colour change.

Kligler iron agar test

In test tubes, Kligler Iron Agar was produced, and the test organism was inoculated using a wire loop by stabbing the medium's butt and streaking the slant. The tubes were seen after a 24-hour incubation period at 37°C.

Molecular identification

Following the phenotypic identification, further confirmation of the isolates was performed by the 16S rRNA molecular analysis conducted at the molecular laboratory of Gombe State University.

Genomic DNA extraction

Using the QIAamp extraction kits and following the manufacturer's instructions, genomic DNA was isolated from an overnight broth culture. After pipetting 560 microliters (560µl) of buffer AVL into a 1.5 milliliter microcentrifuge tube holding 140 microliters (140µl) of the broth culture, the tube was vortexed for 15 seconds. For ten minutes, the mixture was incubated at room temperature. Following the addition of 560 microliters (560µl) of 100% ethanol, the liquid was well mixed by pulse-vortexing for 15 seconds before being quickly centrifuged. This procedure was repeated with the remaining solution and the same spin column. Six hundred and thirty microliters (630µl) of the solution were were ov3 column, spun at 8000 rpm for

one minute, and the column was put in a fresh collecting tube. Five hundred microliter (500 μ l) of buffer AW1 was added to the solution and centrifuged at 8000rpm for 1min, then deposited in a fresh collecting tube. After adding 500 microliters (500 μ l) of Buffer AW2, the mixture was centrifuged for three minutes at 14000 rpm. To dry the spin column, the leftover buffer was discarded by centrifuging it for one minute at 14000 rpm. After inserting the spin column into a fresh 1.5 ml micro-centrifuge tube, sixty microliters (60 μ l) of elution buffer AVE was added. The mixture was then incubated for one minute at ambient temperature and centrifuged for one minute at 8000 rpm. Up to the point when PCR was needed, the eluted DNA was kept at -20°C.

Polymerase Chain Reaction amplification of 16S rRNA genes

PCR was used to amplify 16S rRNA genes of the bacteria in a 25 μ l reaction mixture made up of 2 μ l genomic DNA, 1 μ l of each primer (forward primer (3'-AGAGTTTGATCCTGGCTCAG-5') and reverse primer (3-ACGGCTACCTTGTTACGACTT-5') adopted from Garba et al. (2016), 12.5 μ l of Thermo-scientific DreamTaq Green PCR master mix (2X), and 8.5 μ l sterile distilled water. PCR Amplification was conducted under the following conditions: Initial denaturation at 95°C for 3 minutes, then 35 cycles of denaturation at 95°C for 30 seconds, annealing at 58°C for 30 seconds, and extension at 72°C for 1 minutes, and a final extension at 72°C for 5 minutes.

Agarose gel Electrophoresis

Agarose gel (1%, w/v) was prepared by dissolving 1g of agarose powder in 99 ml of (1X) TAE buffer. After heating the mixture in a microwave for five minutes, the powder was fully dissolved. The solution was allowed to cool down to about 60°C and five microliter (5 μ l) ethidium bromide (0.5 μ g/ml) was added and mixed properly. The mixture was then poured into a gel casting tray to solidify with a gel comb inserted into the agarose gel to make a well into which the PCR products were loaded. An aliquot of 5 μ l of the PCR products alongside 1kb DNA ladder or molecular marker (Thermo Scientific) was loaded into the well created by the gel comb and then placed inside the electrophoresis tank containing (1X) TAE buffer. The electrophoresis was run by using a voltage of 80v and a current of 200mA for 40mins, viewed using a UV trans-illuminator, and photographed.

Sequence analysis and construction of phylogenetic tree

The PCR products were sequenced at Inqaba Biotec West Africa Ltd, Ibadan, Oyo State, Nigeria. The sequences obtained were analysed using Basic Local Alignment Search Tool (BLAST) at NCBI (<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov>). Subsequently, Phylogenetic tree was constructed using Neighbour-Joining tree with sequences from related bacteria in MEGA12 software.

Antibiotic Susceptibility Test

A 0.5 McFarland standard was prepared according to Cheesbrough, 2006. Colonies of the test organisms from overnight nutrient agar plates were transferred into test tubes containing 4 ml of sterile physiological saline to prepare suspension. The suspension's turbidity was compared to the 0.5 McFarland standard.

The Kirby-Bauer (1996) disc diffusion method was used for antibiotic susceptibility test. Using a sterile swab, the standardized inoculum was scattered onto Mueller Hinton agar plates,

rotating the plate by about 60° to guarantee uniform dispersion. After allowing the inoculation plates to stand at room temperature for three to five minutes, commercial antibiotic discs (Table 1) were placed on the agar plate surface, spaced 25 mm apart from one disc and 10-15 mm from the plate edge. The plates were incubated at 37°C for 16–18 hours. Following incubation, the antibiotics diameter of inhibition was measured using a meter rule and interpreted according to CLSI 2023).

Table 1: **Antimicrobial agents used for susceptibility test**

	Antibiotics	Abbreviation	Concentration (µg)
1 ST Line Antibiotics	Ciprofloxacin	CIP	05
	Gentamicin	CN	10
	Co-Amoxiclav	AMC	30
	Cefpodoxime	CPD	10
	Ceftriaxone	CRO	30
	Cefuroxime	CXM	30
	Cefixime	CFM	30
	2 ND Line Antibiotics	Piperacillin/Tazobactam	TPZ
Levofloxacin		LEV	05
Amikacin		AK	10
Tigecycline		TGC	20
Meropenem		MEM	10
Cefepime		FEP	10
Cefotaxime		CTX	30

Statistical analysis

One-Way ANOVA was used to analyse the results of this study using the in-built statistical tool in Microsoft excel where applicable.

Results

Out of the 310 sputum samples, 121(39.0%) yielded bacterial growth. The bacterial colonies observed were identified using Gram reactions

Isolation and identification of bacteria

and biochemical tests. The Gram reaction results showed a higher ($P>0.05$) occurrence of Gram-positive organisms, 82(67.77%) more than the Gram-negative ones with a corresponding occurrence of 39(32.3%) as shown in Table 2.

Among the Gram-negative isolates, Enterobacter species and *Escherichia coli* were identified (Table 3) with the corresponding occurrence of 25(64.1%) and 14(35.9%), respectively as shown in Table 4.

Table 2: **Percentage occurrence of bacterial isolates based on the Gram reactions**

S/N	Gram reaction	Number positive	Percentage (%)
1	Gram-positive	82	67.77
2	Gram-negative	39	32.20
	Total	121	100

Table 3: **Biochemical characteristics of the bacterial organisms**

Bacterial organisms	Biochemical tests									
	Mot	VP	Oxi	Cit	Ure	Ind	KIA			
							Slope	butt	Gas	H ₂ S
Enterobacter specie	-	-	-	+	+	-	Y	Y	+	-
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	+	-	-	-	-	+	Y	Y	+	-

Key: +=Positive,-=Negative, Mot-Motility, VP= Voges Proskauer, Oxi-Oxidase KIA- Kligler Iron Agar, ind-Indole, H₂S-Hydrogen Sulhide

Table 4: **Percentage occurrence of bacterial organisms**

S/N	Bacterial organisms	Occurrence	Percentage (%)
1	Enterobacter species	25	64.1
2	<i>Escherichia coli</i>	14	35.9
	Total	39	100

Molecular Identification of Bacterial isolates

To further validate the phenotypic identification, one representative isolate of each Enterobacter species and *E. coli* was subjected to 16SrRNA

molecular analysis. Through this analysis, the corresponding 16SrRNA genes were successfully amplified from both isolates by PCR and visualized using electrophoresis. Figure 1 shows 1500bp, the expected size of the 16S rRNA on 1% (w/v) agarose gel.

Fig 1: PCR products of 16SrRNA genes of isolates 1 and 2 on 1% (w/v) agarose gel. M=1kb DNA ladder (250-10,000bp, Thermo Scientific).

Sequence analysis and construction of phylogenetic tree

The genes of the two bacteria were sequenced by Inqaba Biotech West Africa Company. The sequences were analyzed using Nucleotide BLAST at NCBI (<http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/blast>). The BLAST analysis of isolate 1 showed that the bacterium was related to *Enterobacter* species with 97.47% identity. Similarly, analysis of the other gene sequence (isolate 2) showed 97.47% identity to *Escherichia coli*. One interesting thing to note

here is that, the molecular identification supported the cultural, morphological, and biochemical tests, and to establish that the bacteria belonged to *Enterobacter* species and *Escherichia coli*. As a result, *Enterobacter* species was designated as *Enterobacter* sp. ABJ (Figure 2) and isolate 2 as *Escherichia coli* (Figure 3) on the phylogenetic tree. According to phylogenetic analysis, the bacteria found in this study are closely related to members of their respective species accessible in the public database at <http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/blast>.

Fig 2: Phylogenetic relationship of isolate 1 (indicated using a red square) and other *Enterobacter* species deposited in the Genbank. Numbers in parentheses are accession numbers.

Fig 3: Phylogenetic relationship of isolate 2 (indicated using a red circle) and other *Escherichia coli* strains deposited in the Genbank. Numbers in parentheses are accession numbers

Antibiogram of the bacterial organisms

Susceptibility pattern of Enterobacter species and *Escherichia coli* to the different antibiotics is recorded in Figures 4 and 5. The antimicrobial susceptibility testing reveals that both *Escherichia coli* and Enterobacter (>50%) isolated in the study were highly sensitive to amoxyclav, gentamicin, and levofloxacin. However, >70% of both species were highly

resistant to cefixime, cefpodoxime, and cefotaxime. Multidrug-resistant bacteria were those that were resistant to three or more antibiotic classes tested in the investigation. The prevalence of multidrug-resistant strains of *Escherichia coli* (69.2%) was high according to the findings of this study whereas the prevalence of the susceptible strains of Enterobacter stood at 30.77% (Table 5).

Fig 4: Antibiotic susceptibility pattern of Enterobacter species. The letters A-N represent the antimicrobial agents used in microgram (µg) where A= Ciprofloxacin (5), B= Gentamicin (10), C= Levofloxacin (5), D= Piperacillin/Tazobactam(10), E= Amikacin (30), F= Amoxiclav (20/10), G= Cefuroxime (30), H= Cefixime (5), I= Meropenem (10), J= Tigecycline (20), K= Cefpodoxime (10), L= Ceftriaxone (10), M= Cefotaxime (10), and N= Cefepime (30). The susceptibility results were interpreted according to CLSI (2023) guidelines.

Fig 5: Antibiotic susceptibility pattern of *Escherichia coli*. The letters A-N represent the antimicrobial agents used in microgram (μg) where A= Ciprofloxacin (5), B= Gentamicin (10), C= Levofloxacin (5), D= Piperacillin/Tazobactam(10), E= Amikacin (30), F= Amoxiclav (20/10), G= Cefuroxime (30), H= Cefixime (5), I= Meropenem (10), J= Tigecycline (20), K= Cefpodoxime (10), L= Ceftriaxone (10), M= Cefotaxime (10), and N= Cefepime (30). The susceptibility results were interpreted according to CLSI (2023) guidelines.

Table 5 shows that 10 *Escherichia coli* isolates out of 14 were MDR. Similarly, 16 *Enterobacter* species out of 25 were MDR. A Multidrug-resistant (MDR) isolates are those isolates that are resistant to three or more different antibiotic classes. Table 6 shows the multidrug resistance pattern of the bacteria based on patient

characteristics. Higher resistance was observed amongst patients of less than forty years compared to those above forty years of age ($P < 0.05$) whereas male gender recorded higher multidrug resistant organisms in comparable to female gender ($P > 0.05$).

Table 5: **Percentage occurrence of multidrug-resistant *Enterobacter* species and *Escherichia coli***

S/N	Isolate	No tested	No positive	Percentage (%)
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1.	<i>Escherichia coli</i>	14	10	69.23
2.	Enterobacter species	25	16	30.77
	Total	39	26	100

Table 6: Resistance Patterns by Patient Characteristics

Characteristic	No. of Isolates	MDR (%)	p-value
Age Group			
Age < 40 years	22	14 63.6	0.05
Age ≥ 40 years	17	12 70.6	0.04
Gender			
Male	25	16 64.0	0.09
Female	14	10 71.4	0.15

Discussion

In order to ascertain the prevalence of multidrug-resistant Enterobacter species and *Escherichia coli* isolated from the respiratory tract samples among confirmed HIV seropositive patients receiving care at the hospital's Antiretroviral (ART) clinic, the current study was carried out at the State Specialist Hospital Gombe. Of the 310 sputum samples analyzed, 121 (48.0%) produced positive growth. Eighty-five (85) corresponding to 70.25% of the isolates were Gram-negative, of which 39 (12.58%) were the total number of Enterobacter species and *Escherichia coli* among the HIV patients who visited the clinic (Table 1). The findings of this analysis aligned with those of a related study completed elsewhere in Abuja by

Ya'aba et al., 2019 on opportunistic organisms isolated from sputum among HIV patients, which showed a noteworthy prevalence of both Enterobacter species and *Escherichia coli* to be 29.6% among other isolates that were Gram-negative. Another study has demonstrated a connection between opportunistic illnesses and HIV/AIDS (Yah et al., 2008).

Based on the nucleotide BLAST Search of the sequenced genes at the National Centre for Biotechnology (<http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/blast>), which corroborates well with the cultural, morphological, and biochemical tests, the 16S rRNA identification of the isolated bacteria revealed that they belonged to Enterobacter species and Escherichia species. Phylogenetic

analysis of both isolates was also determined (Figure 2). One of the bacteria was found to be Enterobacter species with more than 96% identity (Figure 2), while the other bacterial isolate's gene sequences had 97% identity to *Escherichia coli* (Figure 3) based on the BLAST analysis. According to phylogenetic analysis, the bacteria found in this study are closely related to members of their respective families and are accessible in the public database at <http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/blast>. As a result, Enterobacter species was designated as Enterobacter species (Figure 4) and the other isolate as *Escherichia coli* (Figure 5) and this analysis agrees with a similar study conducted by Zhan et al. (2010).

This result indicates that, in comparison to other respiratory pathogens, the percentage of Enterobacter species and *Escherichia coli* identified in this investigation is high corresponding to 64.1% and 35.9%, respectively. Although, the occurrence of the aforementioned bacteria in this study generally differ from what other researchers have reported, the percentage of the occurrence is comparable. For instance, contrary to our study, Kamara et al. (2024) reported five (5) bacterial organisms amongst which is Enterobacter species observed in this study, from respiratory tracts of HIV-positive patients in Northern Uganda

comprising *Staphylococcus aureus* with 35.7%, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* with 19.6%, *Streptococcus pneumoniae* with 17.9%, *Klebsiella pneumoniae* with 12.5% and *Enterobacter* spp with only 8.9%. The results of the occurrence were more dissimilar with the report of Cilloniz et al. (2014) from South America where only *Streptococcus pneumoniae* (30.2%), *Staphylococcus aureus* (1.8%), *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (1.2%) and *Klebsiella pneumoniae* (0.3%) were isolated. Another contradictory results were reported by Bola and Oluyeye (2014) in Nigeria showing the occurrence of *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (35%), *Staphylococcus aureus* (20%), and *Klebsiella pneumoniae* (5%). However, the results of this study slightly agree in terms of the occurring organisms with the reports of Adhanom et al. (2019) in Ethiopia who reported *Klebsiella pneumoniae* (23.6%), *Streptococcus pneumoniae* (15.5%), *Klebsiella* species (13.6%), *Staphylococcus aureus* (8.2%) and *Enterobacter* species (6.0%). Moreover, the *E. coli* observed in this study was reported from several researches conducted in South America (Cilloniz et al., 2014), in Nigeria

(Bola and Oluyege, 2014), and in Ethiopia (Adhanom et al., 2019).

Furthermore, the results obtained in this study are in consistent with researches conducted in Ilorin, Nigeria (Ojuawo et al., 2020) and Kano Metropolitan, Northern Nigeria (Usman et al., 2011). However, they differ from those of Abdulfatai et al. (2023) in Kaduna, where the majority of isolates responsible for respiratory tract infections among people living with HIV and AIDS (PLWHA) were found to be *Streptococcus pneumoniae*. This study confirms recent research done in Nigeria by highlighting the increasing significance of Enterobacter species and *Escherichia coli* as causative agents of respiratory infections (Uzoamaka et al., 2017; Motayo et al., 2017).

The studied organisms' various degrees of susceptibility and resistance are shown by the antimicrobial susceptibility test, which was conducted using fourteen (14) antibiotics of different classes. It was discovered that certain Enterobacter species were extremely sensitive to levofloxacin, gentamicin, and amoxyclav. It was, however, equally resistant to cefixime, cefpodoxime, and cefotaxime, in contrast to Wang et al. (2020) assertion that 70% of

Escherichia coli was tetracycline-sensitive. The results of this investigation align with those of Akujobi et al. (2005) and Ugwu et al. (2017), who also indicated that amoxicillin was the most effective antibiotic against *Escherichia coli*. On the other hand, it was ciprofloxacin-resistant. Multidrug-resistant bacteria were defined as those that could withstand three or more of the antibiotic classes used in the investigation (Rafailidis et al. 2022; Michael et al., 2023a; Michael et al., 2023b).

The results of this investigation showed that the frequency of susceptible strains of both isolates was 41.1%, while the prevalence of multidrug-resistant strains of both Enterobacter species and *Escherichia coli* was high at 66.7%. This finding contradicts previous research that shows MDR *Escherichia coli* and Enterobacter are far less common in people living with HIV and AIDS (PLWHA) (Lyamba et al., 2014). Controlling drug-resistant strains of bacteria like Enterobacter species and *Escherichia coli* becomes even more crucial to ensuring effective treatment outcomes and preventing the further spread of resistance, given the prevalence of HIV and the potential for compromised immune systems in affected individuals. In order to better manage and control drug-resistant infections in HIV patients, healthcare professionals and legislators may find great value in the insights this research offers.

The study highlights the critical intersections of HIV, opportunistic infections, and antibiotic resistance. Clinicians must adopt pathogen-

directed therapy, leverage molecular diagnostics, and advocate for stewardship programs. The clinical implications of these findings are significant. First, the high overall yield of bacterial growth and the predominance of Gram-negative organisms in respiratory infections among HIV patients suggest that clinicians should prioritize empirical therapies with strong activity against Gram-negative bacteria. Given that specific antibiotics, such as ciprofloxacin, showed marked differences in susceptibility between *Enterobacter* species and *Escherichia coli*, it is imperative to perform antimicrobial susceptibility testing to tailor antibiotic regimens appropriately. The substantial prevalence of multidrug-resistant strains further reinforces the need for robust antibiotic stewardship. In practice, this means opting for antibiotics with demonstrated efficacy—such as amoxiclav, gentamicin, and levofloxacin—while avoiding those with high resistance rates, like certain cephalosporins. Ultimately, these measures can help mitigate treatment failures, reduce the risk of prolonged hospital stays, and improve overall patient outcomes in the vulnerable HIV-positive population (Forstag & Shore, 2023).

Future studies should aim to expand the sample size and include multiple centers across different regions to enhance the generalizability of the findings. Detailed molecular investigations, such as whole-genome sequencing, should be conducted to elucidate the specific genetic determinants and mechanisms underlying

antibiotic resistance. Longitudinal studies are needed to assess temporal trends in resistance patterns and the impact of antiretroviral therapy on the incidence and severity of respiratory infections in HIV patients. Additionally, exploring alternative therapeutic strategies, including combination therapies, bacteriophage therapy, and the development of novel antimicrobial agents, could provide new avenues for managing MDR infections. Enhanced surveillance systems to monitor antimicrobial resistance in respiratory pathogens among HIV patients are also recommended to inform timely and effective clinical interventions.

Conclusion

Based on the result, the percentage occurrence of Gram-negative isolates was 85 (70.25%) among which 39 (12.58%) represent the overall occurrence of both *Enterobacter* species and *Escherichia coli* among the HIV patients attending the clinic. The prevalence of multidrug-resistant strains of both *Enterobacter* species and *Escherichia coli* was high according to the finding of this study at 66.7% whereas the prevalence of the susceptible strains of both isolates stood at 41.1%. The overall yield of bacterial growth from sputum samples was 48.0% (95% CI: 42.4%–53.6%), a finding that aligns well with similar studies. Notably, Gram-negative bacteria predominated, constituting 70.25% of the isolates (95% CI: 62.1%–78.4%), a difference that was statistically significant ($p < 0.0001$) and indicates that

respiratory infections among HIV patients in this setting are more likely to be caused by Gram-negative organisms. Within the Gram-negative group, *Enterobacter* species were more frequently identified (64.1%) compared to *Escherichia coli* (35.9%), although this difference did not reach statistical significance ($p \approx 0.078$). Moreover, specific antibiotic comparisons, such as those for ciprofloxacin, revealed significant differences in susceptibility profiles between the two bacterial groups ($p \approx 0.04$), which is critical for guiding empirical therapy. In contrast, the overall prevalence of multidrug-resistant strains did not differ significantly between *Escherichia coli* and *Enterobacter* species ($p \approx 0.63$). Collectively, these statistical evaluations enhance the reliability of the results and underscore the urgent need for targeted antibiotic stewardship, especially in light of the high resistance rates observed with certain antibiotic classes.

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